

Field screening of rice varieties against gall midge and rice tungro virus

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In the national screening nursery of kharif 1975, 1,223 selections originating from various research stations were screened against gall midge (*Pachytiplosis oryzae*), and against rice tungro virus and its green leafhopper vector (*Nephotettix virescens* and *N. apicalis*) under high natural pressure. Screening was carried out at Chiplima, a hot spot for both rice tungro virus disease and gall midge. Entries were scored on the standard

0–9 scale. Gall midge incidence was heavy.

A high buildup of the green leafhopper was accompanied by epidemic rice tungro virus disease. Only 57 of the entries survived at 50 days after planting. On the 80th day after planting, 18 varieties seemed to promise multiple resistance to the pest and the disease (see table), and survived until harvest. Only one variety, designated 52094 (IR8/MTU10), showed immunity to gall midge; three varieties, RP974-210-10-8, CRM14-29-R-75, and IR2071-621-2-3, were highly tolerant of the rice tungro virus disease.

Another strain, designated as “T” strain, was reported from the Philippines by Rivera in 1970. This strain produces interveinal stripes on FK 135 but causes much less stunting than the “S” strain or even the “M” strain. The characteristic symptom of the “T” strain is the narrowing of leaves in rice cultivars TN1, IR5, IR8, and IR22.

Subsequent studies in India revealed the occurrence of five distinct strains of RTV, introducing complexity in strain differentiation and nomenclature. Shastry reported the occurrence of two strains in 1972 and designated them as RTV₁ and RTV₂. Anjaneyulu and John provided evidence of the existence of four RTV strains in India in 1972. They retained RTV₁ as such, divided RTV₂ into the two distinct strains of RTV_{2A} and RTV_{2B}, and designated a new strain as RTV₃. All four Indian strains behaved like the “S” strain on differentials used by Rivera and Ou in 1967, but were separable on the Indian set of differentials consisting of TN1, Pankhari 203, Ambemohar 102, Ambemohar 159, Kamod 253, and Latisail. Another Indian strain, designated as RTV₄, was detected and characterized by Mishra, Niazi, Basu, Ghosh, and Raychandhuri in 1976.

Rice varieties showing multiple resistance to gall midge (GM) and rice tungro virus disease (RTV) in national screening nursery at Regional Research Station, Chiptima, kharif 1975.

Designation	Cross	Reaction ^a to	
		GM	RTV
RP10-2	IR8/PTB10	3	3
RP633-9-5-8-1	(IR8/BJ1-43) × IR22	4	2
R2353	W1263/CR10-4011	3	4
JR mutant 2-25-4	Rexoro/R11	3	3
TNAU13610	Co Mutant	3	3
RP974-112-1-6	Sona/RP9-4	2	3
RP974-210-10-8	"	2	1
32343	W1263/Tella Hamsa	3	2
52094	IR8/MTU10	0	2
CRM14-29-R-75	W1263/SM1-6	3	1
RP825-71-4-9	Vijaya/PTB21	3	3
RP825-71-4-10	"	3	4
RP825-71-4-11	"	4	2
RP825-71-4-1	"	3	3
RP825-71-4-4	"	3	4
IR2071-875-2-3-4		2	4
IR2071-621-2-3		2	1
IR2071-747-6-3-2 (IR32)		2	4
<i>Susceptible checks:</i>			
for gall midge – Jaya		9	–
for RTV – TN1		–	9

^aEntries were scored for resistance on the standard 0–9 scale: 0–3 = good or high; 4–6 = fair or intermediate; 7–9 = poor or low.

A proposed key to the strains of rice tungro virus

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Since studies on the strains of rice tungro virus (RTV) began in 1967, eight strains have been reported from the Philippines and India. On the basis of the plant symptoms and the varietal reaction to

these strains, we propose a key to characterization of the strains.

In 1967, Rivera and Ou reported two strains of RTV which they designated as “S” and “M” strains. The two strains are differentiable on Acheh, FK 135, and Pacita, which respond to the “S” strain by developing symptoms of conspicuous interveinal chlorosis. The “M” strain produces mottling but not the yellowish stripes characteristic of the “S” strain. Further, the infection by the “S” strain causes much more stunting of FK 135 than does infection by the “M” strain.

A key to the strains of RTV (see figure) gives an idea of the latest position in this regard. The “T” strain and all the Indian strains have been grouped here under “S” strain on the basis of the reaction of FK 135.

Because of anomalies in nomenclature of the RTV strains, we propose the following modifications: Leaving the “M” strain as such, the various constituents of the “S” strain complex should be designated as “S” in numerical sequence. Accordingly, the strains presently known as “T”, RTV₁, RTV_{2A}, RTV_{2B}, RTV₃, and RTV₄ should be designated as S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, S₅, and S₆, respectively. That would systematize the available information.

A more comprehensive treatment of the subject is not yet possible because the RTV strains in various countries have not yet been identified. The situation calls for immediate study of strain differentiation on a global scale with due care to

Entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) showing moderately resistant reaction to sheath blight and their cross reactions to bacterial blight and bacterial leaf streak at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Designation	Sheath blight ^a	Bacterial blight ^b	Bacterial leaf streak ^c
BR 20-28-2	5.3	8	2
BR 51-74-2	5.8	5	3
B 189b-29-4-3-1	5.3	7	3
B 462 b-Pn-1-3	4.5	7	3
IR578-95-1-3	6.0	4	4
IR1514 A-E 562-2	5.5	5	3
IR1704-13-3-2	5.9	8	3
IR2031-238-4-2-2-3	4.5	8	3
IR2058-74-2-1	4.6	6	3
IR2063-65-2-1	5.3	6	3
IR2068-65-3	4.3	9	2
IR2070-210-3-3-4	5.7	6	2
IR2070-439-3-4	5.1	6	2
IR2071-176-1-5-2	4.6	6	3
IR2172-64	5.5	6	2
IR2307-62-4-1	4.2	7	2
IR2328-27-3-6	5.4	5	3
IR2561-58-1	4.5	4	3
IR2562-17-4	3.7	6	3
IR2688-43-4-3	5.8	8	2
IR2755-E2-11-1-4	5.0	5	2
IR2760-E1-33-1-2	5.5	6	3
IR2793-15-2	5.5	6	3
IR2796-95-1	6.0	6	2
IR2844-5-2	4.0	7	3
IR2844-27-2	4.3	6	3
A 12-167-3	5.5	9	3
BW 196	5.4	7	3
Biplab	4.2	5	4
IR2070-423-2-5-6	4.8	6	3
Bahagia	5.3	9	3
IR480-5-9-3	4.9	9	3
Ob 5.677	5.2	8	3
IR20	5.0	6	3
IR2153-26-3-5-2	5.6	6	3
IR1917-3-10-3	5.4	7	3
IR1917-3-19-2	5.1	8	3

^aLength of infection spread in cm.

^bRated on a scale of 0–9; 0 = no infection.

^cRated on a scale of 0–4; 0 = no infection.

extent of infection (total length of the diseased area in cm) was recorded. The entries were grouped tentatively by the following grade system: 1.0 to 3.0 cm, resistant; 3.1 to 6.0 cm, moderately resistant; 6.1 to 8.0 cm, moderately susceptible; and 8.1 cm and above, susceptible.

Only 37 of the entries showed moderate resistance to sheath blight at Cuttack (see table). No entry was graded resistant to sheath blight and no entry was uniformly resistant to sheath blight, bacterial blight, and bacterial leaf streak.

Key to the strains of rice tungro virus. Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India.

A ₁	FK 135 shows mottling and no distinct interveinal stripes	M strain
A ₂	FK 135 shows distinct interveinal stripes	S strain
B ₁	Produces distinct narrowing of leaves in TN1	T strain
B ₂	No narrowing of leaves in TN1	
C ₁	Pacita susceptible. Latisail, if susceptible, shows foliar symptoms.	
D ₁	Does not infect Ambemohar 159 and Pankhari 203	RTV ₁
D ₂	Infects both Ambemohar 159 and Pankhari 203	RTV _{2A}
E ₁	Latisail resistant	RTV _{2A}
E ₂	Latisail susceptible	
F ₁	Ambemohar 102 and Kamod 253 susceptible. TN1 severely affected initially but later produces green leaves. If not, at least Pankhari 203 and Latisail show masking of symptoms.	RTV _{2B}
F ₂	Ambemohar 102 and Kamod 253 resistant. No such recovery or masking	RTV _{2B}
C ₂	Pacita resistant. Latisail symptomless carrier	RTV ₄

maintain uniformity in experimental material and procedures. The standard set of differentials that we recommend for the purpose consists of Ambemohar 102, Ambemohar 159, FK 135, Kamod 253, Latisail, Pacita, Pankhari 203, and TN1. The differentials should be individually inoculated at the two- to three-leaf stage. To standardize the method of inoculation for determining strains, we suggest that three adults of the vector leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) that have earlier access to an infected plant for 24 hours be allowed to feed on each test seedling for 6 hours. Data on percentage of infection, extent of stunting, foliar coloration, and reduction of tillering should be recorded at 30 and at 60 days after inoculation.

Screening of IRON against sheath blight at CRRI

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Three hundred twenty-two entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery were grown in the field and inoculated by inserting a sterile stem piece colonized by *Corticium sasakii* inside the leaf sheath when the crop was at maximum tillering stage. Very good infection developed in the entries, indicating that in centers such as Cuttack where humidity is very high, the stem-tape-inoculation method need not be used.

At 15 days after inoculation, the